

Generators In-Person Quiz

Coding Question

Write a generator `odd_numbers()` which produces an infinite sequence of odd numbers starting with 1 (i.e., {1, 3, 5, ... })

One solution:

```
def odd_numbers():  
    x = 1  
    while True:  
        yield x  
        x += 2
```

Multiple Choice and Short Response Questions

Question 1:

How is a generator function different than a normal function in Python?

- A generator returns a single value and then terminates, while a regular function can return multiple values.
- A generator can only return values as a list, whereas a regular function returns values one at a time.
- A generator uses the `yield` keyword to produce a series of values over time, while a regular function uses the `return` keyword to produce a single value.
- A generator must be called repeatedly to return all its values, while a regular function returns all its values in one go.

Solution: c

Question 2:

What is the advantage of using a generator over a list?

- Generators store all their values in memory, whereas lists generate values on-the-fly, saving memory.
- Generators can be iterated multiple times, whereas lists can only be iterated once
- Generators generate values one at a time, using less memory than lists which store all values at once

- d. Generators are faster to iterate over because they create all values at the start, while lists generate values as needed

Solution: c

Question 3:

How can you convert a generator to a list? Select all that apply

- a. Using the list() function (e.g., list(my_generator))
- b. Using the convert() method (e.g., my_generator.convert())
- c. Using a for loop and appending items to a list
- d. Using the to_list() method (e.g., my_generator.to_list())

Solution: a, c

Question 4:

Which of the following is/are true about generators? Mark all that apply.

- a. Generators are memory-efficient
- b. Generators can only be iterated once
- c. Generators can be restarted after completion
- d. Generators use the yield keyword to produce values

Solution: a, b, d

Question 5:

What is the name of the exception that is raised when you call next() on an iterator that has no more values? [text response]

Solution: StopIteration

Question 6:

Consider the following block of code. When does the string "starting" get printed out?

```
def my_generator():  
    print("starting")  
    yield "hello world"
```

```
g = my_generator() # (1)
print(next(g))     # (2)
print(next(g))     # (3)
```

- After the line labeled (1) is run
- After the line labeled (2) is run
- After the line labeled (3) is run
- Never

Solution: **b**

Decorators In-Person Quiz

Coding Question

Implement a decorator called `announce` which changes a function's behavior by:

- Printing the string `"start"` before the function runs
- Printing the string `"end"` after the function is complete

NOTE: it's fine if the decorator only works on functions that take no arguments.

One solution:

```
def announce(original_func):
    def new_func():
        print("start")
        original_func()
        print("end")
    return new_func
```

Multiple Choice and Short Response Questions

Question 1:

What is the primary purpose of a Python decorator?

- To create new variables
- To modify the behavior of a function
- To import libraries
- To execute a loop

Solution: b

Question 2:

What happens when you apply a decorator to a function?

- a. The function is executed immediately when the decorator is applied
- b. The function is replaced with the new function defined in the decorator
- c. The function's name is changed to the decorator's name
- d. The function return type is automatically converted to `None`

Solution: b

Question 3:

Which of the following are characteristics of Python decorators? Choose all that apply.

- a. Decorators can only be used with functions that take no arguments
- b. Decorators can modify the behavior of the function it decorates without changing its source code
- c. Decorators can modify both the input and output of a function
- d. Decorators are functions that take another function as an argument

Solution: b, c, d

Question 4:

Consider the following function definition:

```
def f(<ANSWER>):
```

```
...
```

What can you replace <ANSWER> with so that f can take any number of arguments?

[text response]

Solution: *args, **kwargs

Question 5:

What is printed out after line 13 is run? For any error, write "error". For the empty string, write [blank].

```
2 ✓ def enthusiastic(original_func):
3 ✓     def new_func():
4         res = original_func()
5         res += "!!!"
6         return res
7     return new_func()
8
9 @enthusiastic
10 ✓ def greet():
11     return "Hello world"
12
13 print(greet())
14
```

Solution: "error" (function shouldn't be called in L7)

Question 6:

What is printed out after line 9 is run? For any error, write "error". For the empty string, write [blank].

```
1
2 ✓ def f(f1, f2, arg):
3     f1(arg)
4     f2(arg)
5
6 ✓ def g(s):
7     print(s.upper())
8
9 f(print, g, "hello")
```

Solution:

Hello

HELLO

Generators Take-Home Quiz

Multiple Choice and Short Response Questions

Question 1:

What is the advantage of using a generator over a list?

- a. Generators store all their values in memory, whereas lists generate values on-the-fly, saving memory.
- b. Generators are faster to iterate over because they create all values at the start, while lists generate values as needed
- c. Generators can be iterated multiple times, whereas lists can only be iterated once
- d. Generators generate values one at a time, using less memory than lists which store all values at once

Solution: d

Question 2:

Consider the following block of code. When does the string "starting" get printed out?

```
4 ✓ def my_generator():  
5     print("starting")  
6     yield "hello world"  
7  
8 g = my_generator() # (1)  
9 print(next(g))     # (2)  
10 print(next(g))    # (3)  
11 |
```

- a. After the line labeled (1) is run
- b. After the line labeled (2) is run
- c. After the line labeled (3) is run
- d. Never

Solution: b

Question 3:

How can you convert a generator to a list? Select all that apply

- a. Using a for loop and appending items to a list

- b. Using the `convert()` method (e.g., `my_generator.convert()`)
- c. Using the `list()` function (e.g., `list(my_generator)`)
- d. Using the `to_list()` method (e.g., `my_generator.to_list()`)

Solution: a, c

Question 4:

Which of the following is/are true about generators? Mark all that apply.

- a. Generators are memory-efficient
- b. Generators use the `yield` keyword to produce values
- c. Generators can be restarted after completion
- d. Generators can only be iterated once

Solution: a, b, d

Coding Questions

Question 1:

```
1 # Write a generator count_by_two(n) which produces the
2 # infinite sequence of numbers {n, n+2, n+4, ...}
3
4 # Example usage:
5 g = count_by_two(5)
6 print(next(g)) # prints "5"
7 print(next(g)) # prints "7"
8 print(next(g)) # prints "9"
9
10 # YOUR CODE HERE:
11
```

One Solution:

```
def count_by_two(n):
    while True:
        yield n
        n += 2
```

Question 2:

```
1 # Write a generator cycle(n) which generates the infinite sequence {0, 1, ..., n-1, 0, 1, ... }
2 # For example, cycle(3) should produce the sequence {0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2, 0, 1, 2, ... }.
3 # For full points, use both the 'yield from' statement and the 'range' function in your answer.
4
5 # Example usage:
6 c4 = cycle(4)
7 for x in range(5):
8     print(next(c4))
9 # Should print: "0", "1", "2", "3", "0"
10
11
12 # YOUR CODE HERE:
13
```

One Solution:

```
def cycle(n):
    while True:
        yield from range(n)
```

Decorators Take-Home Quiz

Question 1:

What happens when you apply a decorator to a function?

- a. The function is replaced with the new function defined in the decorator
- b. The function's name is changed to the decorator's name
- c. The function is executed immediately when the decorator is applied
- d. The function return type is automatically converted to `None`

Solution: a

Question 2:

Which of the following are characteristics of Python decorators? Choose all that apply.

- a. Decorators can only be used with functions that take no arguments
- b. Decorators can modify the behavior of the function it decorates without changing its source code
- c. Decorators are functions that take another function as an argument
- d. Decorators can modify both the input and output of a function

Solution: b, c, d

Question 3:

Consider the following function definition:

```
def f(<ANSWER>):
```

...

What can you replace <ANSWER> with so that f can take any number of arguments?

Solution: *args, **kwargs

Question 4:

What is printed out after line 8 is run? For any error, write "error". For the empty string, write [blank].

```
2 ✓ def apply(f, arg):  
3     f(arg)  
4  
5 ✓ def g(x):  
6     print(x)  
7  
8     apply(g(), "hi")
```

Solution: error [Explanation: g should not be called in line 8]

Question 5:

What is printed out after line 9 is run? For any error, write "error". For the empty string, write [blank].

```
2 ✓ def f(f1, f2, arg):  
3     f1(arg)  
4     f2(arg)  
5  
6 ✓ def g(s):  
7     print(s.upper())  
8  
9     f(print, g, "hello")
```

Solution:

hello
HELLO

Coding Questions

Question 1:

```
1 # Write a decorator called 'print_time' which alters a function by
2 # printing out how many seconds it took to run each time the function
3 # is called. Your decorator only needs to work for functions with no arguments.
4 #
5 # HINT: you can get the current time by using: time.time()
6
7 # Example Usage:
8 @print_time
9 def f():
10     y = 0
11     for x in range(100000000):
12         y += 1
13
14 f() # might print "5.491" indicating ~5.5 seconds
15
16 # YOUR CODE HERE:
17
```

One Solution:

```
import time

def print_time(orig_func):
    def new_func():
        t = time.time()
        orig_func()
        print(time.time() - t)
    return new_func
```

Question 2:

```
1 # Define a decorator called 'question(n)' which takes a parameter (n)
2 # and adds n question-marks to the result of a function. It only needs
3 # to work on functions that take no arguments and return strings.
4
5 # Example Usage:
6 @question(3)
7 def hi():
8     return "hi"
9
10 print(hi()) # prints: "hi???"
11
12 # YOUR CODE HERE:
```

One Solution:

```
def question(n):
    def question_n(old_func):
        def new_func():
            return old_func() + "?"*n
        return new_func
    return question_n
```